

**Deliverable D JIP2-1.6
Twelve Month Report 2019**

**JIP2 - COHESIVE - IA2 - 1st Call
Workpackage 1**

Responsible Partner: RIVM

12 MONTH PERIODIC REPORT (2019)

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1. Summary of the work carried out

Two main events in 2019 were the annual meeting that was held on April 10-12 at SVA and the general meeting on November 27-29 in Rome at ISS. For an integrative project as COHESIVE, coming together and extensively discuss issues is very important. One element, in addition to work on the content of the project, is getting to know each other and build trust and respect. Since the whole project is built around strengthening collaboration between med-vet-food in the area of zoonotic diseases, realizing the value of this collaboration in an international setting is also key nationally. All tasks were discussed and several workshops took place. Also time was reserved to inform stakeholders via a videoconference in both meetings.

WP2: For WP2.1 the main goal is to develop guidelines for *national* One Health structures or other ways to strengthen human-veterinary collaborations, with the aim to improve signalling, risk assessment and response to zoonoses. Since in March 2019 an extended, update version of the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) was published, the focus of the workshop during the annual meeting was shifted towards getting insight in to what extend the new TZG was useful in setting up/strengthening such collaborations in European countries. Although the TZG is useful, added value is seen in a dedicated, simple European guideline with focus on implementation (more practical). During meetings in Brussel and London steps were made drafting the implementation guideline. Contact has been made with the FAO group involved in the TZG and we are in the process how to shape the collaboration. During the general meeting in Rome, the focus was on 'political will' as this was indicated during several occasion as a barrier for implementation of activities.

For WP2.2 the goal is to develop a tool to help decide which tool/model best to use for risk assessment in a specific situation. An early prototype decision tree has been developed in excel, using a limited number of publicly available quantitative risk assessment tools and also includes disease prioritization tools. To make the application easily accessible and available (avoiding proprietary software) a version in R-Shiny is being made. A webinar was held on 6th September for partners in COHESIVE to introduce the tool ahead of the workshop during the general meeting. Input from the workshop is going to be used to further improve and refine the tool.

WP3.1: A workshop was held on WP3.1 during the annual meeting, focusing on how information around an event/outbreak is shared. It was concluded that detailed descriptions of systems may not be very helpful for other countries trying to build up new systems/ways to share signals. Rather, it may be more useful to identify different factors that are believed to contribute to well-functioning systems/ways to share signals, trying to answer "why does signal sharing work well in this context". An interview guideline has been made and in-depth interviews are in being held. Currently, the interviews are analysed.

For WP3.2 the first task was to make an inventory and analysis of horizon scanning tools. Evaluation of a questionnaire has been conducted, literature inventory and workshops have been performed within the task to identify horizon scanning tools. An important tool is the formation of an expert team. A horizon scanning exercise has taken place with the formed team during the general meeting. The different elements that can be drivers of change for One Health issues were discussed as well as current and future challenges.

For WP3.3 systematic mapping of zoonoses detection systems within the UK has been started. By using a reversal process we are starting with identifying the formal outputs of systems that are based around, or contain, zoonoses information.

WP4: For WP4.1 a survey has been conducted in order to gather detailed information on existing databases and information systems for WGS data management and analysis adopted or available among countries. A demo version of the COHESIVE prototype information system (CIS) is made and available for Italy, The Netherlands and Norway to perform a feasibility study.

In WP4.2, a list of available tracing tools was compiled, evaluated and published as a web service that can be updated by interested partners in the future (<http://socialcompare.com/en/comparison/tracing-tools-for->

supplychains-4lh89xq0.. Secondly, the physical setup of the tracing web portal with initial features was realised and several prototype modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting were implemented within the portal or are going to be implemented in the upcoming months. Data formats to collect sample and case data were developed. Their visualisation was tested in case studies and in a current outbreak.

For WP4.3 the goal is to make a platform-independent risk modeling framework. A prototype of the risk modeling framework in R shiny for quantitative microbiological risk assessment has been developed. To make the web application easily available an online version is under development.

2. Work carried out in the JIP, scientific results

WP1: Coordination, communication and sustainability

JIP2-WP1-T1: Coordination (M1-M36)

In 2019, three institutes were welcomed as partners. From Portugal INIAV became a partner, VRI from the Czech Republic and ANSES from France are in the final stage to officially become partner.

COHESIVE has produced a DMP (data-management plan) which will be kept updated through-out the project. There have been several contacts with EFSA and ECDC, mainly concerning WP4. Also regular video-conferences will be organized between the contact persons of EFSA/ECDC and the coordinator of COHESIVE. ORION and NOVA were identified as other OH EJP projects to which COHESIVE could relate. The coordinator of COHESIVE was present at (part of) the ORION annual meeting. ORION, NOVA and COHESIVE are working together at a glossary including terms used within the different projects.

JIP2-WP1-T2: Communication/dissemination (M1-M36)

An annual meeting was organized in April 2019 at SVA in Sweden and a general meeting was organized in November 2019 at ISS in Rome. During the meetings several workshops were organized. There was also the possibility for stakeholders to listen in during the plenary sessions. In Sweden a dedicated session was organized for stakeholders, in which the progression of the COHESIVE project was presented via a videoconference.

The COHESIVE project delivered text for three newsletters, for information on the OH-EJP website and used twitter and linkedin. The coordinator presented the project at the PMC meeting and also at the POC meeting the project was presented. Also during the ASM in Dublin COHESIVE was presented and at the Annual research day at SVA in Sweden. Dissemination activities related to the other workpackages are indicated below.

WP2. Integrated risk-analysis at the national level

JIP2-WP2-T1: Development of guidelines for national One Health structures (M1-M26)

The main goal of this task is the development of guidelines in order to support countries to set up/strengthen the collaboration between the human-vet-food domains with respect to signaling, risk assessment, response and control of zoonoses. During the workshop in November 2018, it was concluded that added value of the guidelines can be found when they would build upon existing guidelines (i.e. Tripartite Zoonoses Guide) and focus on implementation. In March 2019, an updated version of the TZG was published. The workshop in preparation was adjusted in a way to get insight in whether this updated version would fulfil the needs expressed earlier. An intensive workshop led to some conclusions giving direction on how to achieve added value of the implementation guideline. First steps for drafting the implementation guideline were made during the workshop held on July 1st-2nd in Brussel, which was continued during a meeting on October 8-9 in London. Contact has been made with the FAO with respect to the Tripartite Zoonoses Guide (TZG) of OIE, WHO and FAO. COHESIVE visited their SISOT working group meeting on collected tools that support the implementation of the TZG and FAO presented their work in the General Meeting of COHESIVE. Both COHESIVE and FAO see opportunities to collaborate and are enthusiastic to do so. During the general meeting in Rome, a creative session was dedicated to understand what the challenges are in relation to political will within the context of setting up OHRAS as this was identified as one of the major barriers.

The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) has carried out a thematic workshop on 24th April 2019 in Oslo. This workshop has been organised in close cooperation with Norwegian Veterinary Institute (NVI) and the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (NFSA). The large participation of Medical Doctors from all four Norwegian regions but also One Health epidemiological experts from different public agencies (NIPH, NVI and NFSA) contributed to a successful outcome of this event (totally 57 participants). The focus of the workshop was to update participants on common procedures and tools used to improve the human-veterinary-food safety collaboration in the area of emerging zoonosis and contribute to implementation of

a sustainable integrated One Health structure at the national level. The experts from all three agencies presented best practise examples used in Norway on both national and regional level and engaged participants in practical exercises in food born disease outbreak investigation.

JIP2-WP2-T2: Development of structured decision making (M1-M18)

For WP2.2 the goal is to develop a tool to help decide which tool/model best to use for risk assessment in a specific situation. An early prototype decision tree has been developed in HTML, using a limited number of publicly available quantitative risk assessment tools and also includes disease prioritization tools. A webinar was held on 6th September for partners in COHESIVE to introduce the tool. At the general meeting a session was held looking at the questions developed for the decision tree within the tool. The participants were mainly focused on the priority of requirements for risk analysis techniques. Refining the questions ensures the tool weighs the features of different risk assessment techniques in line with the priorities of the user. Current work is focused on further improvements to the usability and additional content of the tool. The prototype tool was also demonstrated at the general meeting and is now available online for the partners to access and trial.

JIP2-WP2-T3: Knowledge transfer and dissemination (M25-M35)

Different dissemination activities already have taken place. They are separately indicated below. Also, preparation have started for the first pilot in Belgium. In addition, Norway, Italy and Portugal are candidates for a pilot.

WP3.Towards an EU zoonoses structure

JIP2-WP3-T1: "Explore current ways for exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis" (M1-M24)

One of the overall purposes of the task is to find good examples of ways to exchange signals cross disciplines/cross borders and learn from each other. During the workshop in Uppsala in April 2019, it was concluded that detailed descriptions of systems may not be very helpful for other countries trying to build up new systems/ways to share signals. Rather, it may be more useful to identify different factors that are believed to contribute to well-functioning systems/ways to share signals as well as factors that prevent signal sharing, focusing on the persons in the systems rather than the technical or organizational solutions. In depth interviews were believed to capture more relevant information than a written questionnaire.

A common interview guideline was developed before summer and during summer and autumn, persons working at different levels in organization and institutes which may be involved in zoonotic events have been interviewed. Six countries have so far been involved and interviewed approximately five persons in each country. The aim is not to give a full description of systems, but rather collect experience from a sample of persons who in their daily work encounter signals of zoonotic events. In general, the participating countries have experienced that they through the interviews have received new information which is relevant when understanding signal sharing. Thematic analysis is ongoing on both national and joint level. One preliminary theme that has emerged is trust and the importance of knowing someone in person in order to share signals. A scientific manuscript is being drafted.

JIP2-WP3-T2: Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection (M1-M24)

Horizon scanning is defined as a specific foresight methodology that utilizes various steps to identify issues at the edge of current thinking that may have significant impact in the medium to long-term future. The multisectoral nature of horizon scanning provide opportunities for successful out-reach to disseminate key trends for One Health applications. Various horizon scanning methods have been identified and for instance, it turned out that there are different definitions in place.

An inventory of the literature on the tools of horizon scanning was done by searching published peer-reviewed papers and reports from international organisations. A horizon scanning workshop was held in April 10-11, 2019 in Uppsala, Sweden. A report based on the results of the questionnaire on One Health approaches on risk analysis of zoonotic diseases done within COHESIVE, on the inventory of the literature

and on the results of the workshop was compiled and submitted to EJP. The report is available for EJP members but cannot yet be disseminated outside EJP.

There are many mid-long-term phenomena that can cause spread of zoonotic diseases and it is of interest to understand these phenomena, how they evolve over time, how they can be prevented, and how to consider and assess these phenomena. Consequently, horizon scanning requires structured information gathering. A One Health horizon scanning tool is based on assembly of information sources and assembly of analysis teams with assigned topics.

JIP2-WP3-T2: - Extra deliverable

Based on the deliverable from M18 - JIP2-WP3-T2: "Select tools for horizon scanning and signal detection" a method has been proposed to be used in COHESIVE task 3.2 which was published by Wintle et al 2017 and Sutherland et al 2011. An important step in this horizon scanning tool is the formation of an expert team. Within the COHESIVE consortium the most relevant One Health disciplines are represented and by using the experts in COHESIVE a horizon scanning exercise was arranged in Rome 27-29th of November in Rome. The aim was to conduct a horizon scanning pilot exercise to identify "drivers of change" in order to strengthen European One Health. The seven step horizon scanning tool generated a list with "drivers of change" for the next five years including for instance: (i) political and decision maker behavior (ii) people/consumer behavior, (iii) information society, (iv) science, R&D and innovations (v), market behavior (vi), new threats (vii) environment and climate change including water sources, wild life, vectors, and farmed animals. The results from the pilot exercise will be followed up in various dissemination activities.

JIP2-WP3-T3: Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks (M6-M30)

This task started in month 6 of the project. During the kick-off meeting in 2018 potential partners were identified as wanting to contribute to varying degrees depending on the level of data available within individual countries.

The immediate task involved selecting potential pathogens that could be used as case studies. As there was not one single pathogen that each country had experienced an incident with, a list of potential candidates was created. These pathogens were mostly focused on 'orphan zoonoses', defined as zoonoses for which no specific animal-health derived legislation exists. These present a challenge to One Health detection systems as they may not trigger formal intelligence gathering channels, but may still pose a threat to human health.

In order to structure the analysis in a way that all partners could participate (also with limited amount of time) while still producing outputs that are comparable between countries and maximizing the advantage of having several different points of view. For this different systems analysis and operational research frameworks were investigated, however no simple technical solution could be identified.

For WP3.3 systematic mapping of zoonoses detection systems within the UK has been started. By using a reversal process, this work was started by identifying the formal outputs of systems that are based around, or contain, zoonoses information. An outline map of one-health products (publications), actors (competent authorities, supporting institution, for instance) and links between them at multiple regional levels has been drafted. Visualising such a complex system is a challenge but is necessary to identify key components of the systems that represent hubs of One Health activity. As part of the general meeting in November 2019, a workshop was held with collaborating partners to gather partial information on the existing high-level structures and competent authorities within countries. Current activity is based on producing a 'core feature' structure that identifies where there are commonalities between countries.

WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control

JIP2-WP4-T1: Molecular typing data and metadata – database creation

A survey has been conducted in order to gather detailed information on existing databases and information systems for Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS) data management and analysis adopted or available among the Member States. The survey represented a first step for the evaluation of the technical feasibility of the inter-connection of genetic data produced by the laboratories and metadata archives available in each country and to provide the project with a reasoned list of the available Information Systems for WGS data and associated metadata. Eight countries answered to the questionnaire: Sweden, Norway, Belgium, Portugal, The Netherlands, Austria, Czech Republic and Germany. The 75% of countries reported that no OH surveillance system is in place at the moment, but where it exists WGS data are shared.

Proposals as a result from the discussions during the WP4 workshop (held at APHA-Weybridge November 2018) and the questionnaire results have been analysed.

A clearer description of the task 4.1 phases has been presented to EFSA representatives on March 2019 and during the stakeholder meeting at the COHESIVE Annual Meeting (held at Uppsala, April 2019). EFSA declared that Task 4.1 purpose is both clear and interesting to them. Besides Italy, two additional Member States decided to perform the evaluation and feasibility study of the project: The Netherland and Norway.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST1: Workshop on data and DBs (M1-M6)

- This task has been completed, see annual report 2018

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST2: Design and implementation of DBs (M6-M17)

- The prototype COHESIVE Information System (CIS) has been realized and there is an ongoing feasibility in Italy, The Netherlands and Norway. A deliverable (D-JIP2-4.1) for this sub-task has been provided on May 2019. The general CIS system has been released on zenodo. Three virtual machines are available for the Member States involved in the feasibility study:
 - Italy: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_italy/
 - The Netherlands: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_holland/
 - Norway: https://cohesive.izs.it/cis_norway/
- During the Annual Meeting on November 2019 in Rome, has been decided to start the integration among the systems produced by tasks 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST3: Interconnection of the three DBs (M13-M21)

- A deliverable (D-JIP2-4.2) for this sub-task has been provided on September 2019, with the details of integration and harmonization status for each Member State.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST4: Analysis of the systems in involved countries (M11-M22)

- The study of the systems for Italy is in progress. Data structures for data of NRL for *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Campylobacter* are ready. Integration with National Animal Identification and Registration System is available. Integration and harmonization with the human part is ongoing. During the General Meeting on November 2019 in Rome, it has been decided to investigate also Shiga toxin-producing Escherichia coli (STEC) as pathogen besides *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Campylobacter*.
- The study of the systems for Norway is in progress. The pilot is based on *Listeria monocytogenes*. A preliminary feasibility analysis has been conducted. A Bioinformatician from NVI visited IZSAM in November 2019 to carry on the feasibility study. The NVI decided to use CIS as their official information systems for collecting WGS data and reporting analysis.
- The study of the systems for The Netherlands is in progress. The pilot is based on *Listeria monocytogenes* and Hepatitis E virus. A first meeting took place in RIVM and WBVR on July 2019 producing a first draft of the feasibility study. Further analyses have been conducted on September and November 2019.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST5: Filling of DBs (M15-M26)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “Linking of the national databases with the COHESIVE prototype information system and the epidemiological analysis tools”.
- During the General Meeting on November 2019 in Rome, it has been decided to start the activity of integration among the three information systems of the WP4. A telco is planned for the beginning of 2020 followed by face-to-face meeting.

JIP2-WP4-T1-ST6: Design and implementation of pipelines (M21-M32)

- In the new T4.1 description, the sub-task title is “Study of available pipelines”.
- The study is in the preliminary phases
- We are connected with Karin Lagesen from the EJP ORION project, which has a WP specifically dedicated to this activity.

JIP2-WP4-T2: Development of a platform-independent tracing framework (M1-M32)

JIP2-WP4-T2-ST1: Evaluation of all available approaches, algorithms and tools for tracing, epidemiological analysis and visualization combined with WGS data (M1-M12)

In addition to the work performed in 2018, in 2019 we were able to integrate even more available tools. The result is a web-based interactive table-like compilation that compares the functionalities of the software tools found. This table was published on the EJP platform together with a report end of June 2019.

JIP2-WP4-T2-ST2: Programming a software and developing an algorithm (M1-M32)

In subtask 2, several modules for data collection, cleaning, visualisation and reporting – in part developed in the framework of other projects - will be unified in one platform:

- A data collection module
- An interactive analysis module
- A WGS-data integration module
- A reporting module
- A synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL)

The overall status and progress of the whole FCL project can be inspected at <https://foodrisklabs.bfr.bund.de/foodchain-lab>.

The specific status and new software versions of the FCL tracing web portal are deployed automatically to a test server where new features of the tool can be seen live. Currently, the production system of the tracing portal is set up and will be accessible at <https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin> in early 2020.

A first demonstrator of a reporting module – the Rapid Outbreak Assessment (ROA) style – was implemented and integrated in the tracing web portal. The ROA style visualises tracing, sample and case information in a format which is suitable for publishing the results of tracing analyses in outbreak reports such as the EFSA-ECDC Joint Rapid Outbreak Assessments just in one click. For this, a JSON-based data exchange module was developed to import delivery data obtained from EFSA.

A prototype of a data cleaning module was developed as a KNIME server workflow. This module will be implemented in the FCL tracing web portal soon.

A prototype of an online data collection mask for tracing data was developed in the framework of a national project but is not yet integrated in the tracing web portal. The mask is available in multiple languages: German, English, Italian and Norwegian. Currently, a task and user management feature is being developed in the national project which will be integrated into the tracing portal as well.

During summer 2019, a web-security audit of the tracing web portal was conducted in the framework of another European project to ensure secure handling of sensitive information.

JIP2-WP4-T2-ST3: Integration of surveillance and outbreak data into the software platform for analysis (M13-M32)

In several presentations on FoodChain-Lab the audience highlighted the importance for integration of WGS data into tracing network visualisations.

Meetings with public and veterinary health institutes were conducted to clarify data needs e.g. in terms of case, sample and animal movement data.

A case study was developed in which WGS sample data i.e. the phylogenetic distance was implemented within the weight of the stations in the tracing network and visualized via different colors. The functionality was implemented in the FCL desktop application and still needs to be implemented in the tracing web portal.

In a current outbreak investigation the sample status of companies and cases (confirmed/probable/not outbreak strain) was implemented and displayed within the tracing network in the FCL desktop application.

Sample data can be assessed via the data collection mask mentioned before. Furthermore a data format for sample and case data was developed in the JSON format. Both can be displayed within the ROA style mentioned above. Visualisation was tested in the framework of case studies.

JIP2-WP4-T3: Development of a platform-independent risk modeling framework (M1-M33)

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST1: Requirement analysis (M1-M9)

Typical components have been identified that support quantitative microbiological risk assessment, advanced simulation techniques, documentation and extended usability. Selection of minimal models for testing and development is ongoing and will be completed in Q1 2020. The prioritization of building blocks for implementation in web application of risk is finished. Currently, also the search of models and data suitable as case study (ideally with input from project partners) is ongoing.

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST2 Implementation (M10-M30)

Various minimal models from the literature and from project partners were tested and defined. Risk questions and scenarios as well as quantitative risk models were provided by partners in COHESIVE and other EJP projects. As part of the implementation of standards, we were also provided with data sets and use-cases in cooperation with the FLI. Furthermore, in cooperation with project partners we have prioritized different building blocks. For the web application of risk we developed various mocks to define the workflow and the individual steps of the user interface in R shiny.

In the first step we have successfully implemented the one-dimensional Monte-Carlo simulation in the web application. The Prototype of “quantitative Riskanalysis” was developed and is finished. With “quantitative Riskanalysis” different risk models can now be implemented and calculated. The implementation of further statistical methods for quantitative risk assessment is ongoing (this subtask will be finished in Q2 2020).

In cooperation with EFSA and openanalytics, we want to work towards integrating risk (web-based version) into a European platform-independent framework for risk modelling.

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST3: Validation of the risk modelling framework (M19-M33)

Validation of web application is ongoing. The validation depends on the implementation of the app and will be implemented after completion of this work (this subtask will be finished in Q3 2020).

JIP2-WP4-T3-ST4: Deployment of the risk modelling framework (M34-M36)

We are in contact with various scientists in order to test the practical suitability and improve the app. According to current development status, the date of deployment of the risk tool is not at risk.

JIP2-WP4-T4: Dissemination (M25-M36)

Dissemination duties of WP4 achievements start only from M25. Nevertheless, in WP4.2 a lot of dissemination work for FCL and the tracing portal that was set up in COHESIVE was done in the framework of other projects in the years 2018 and 2019 (workshops and presentations on FCL, meetings with stakeholders). In the framework of COHESIVE annual meetings, presentations and workshops for WP4 tools were conducted for the COHESIVE community.

In 2020 a joint workshop on WP4 tools and how they interact is envisioned as a satellite event for the COHESIVE annual meeting open for the COHESIVE community and other interested users. WP4 activities might also be presented at the 2020 OHEJP Annual Scientific Meeting in Prague.

3. Progress of the research project: milestones and deliverables

Deliverables

JIP name	Project deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery date from AWP	Actual delivery date	If deliverable not submitted on time: Forecast delivery date	Comments
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-1.3	Annual meeting	14	12-04-2019		
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-1.4	Annual report	16	18-01-2019		
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-2.3	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18	31-12-2019		Prototype is developed. Webinar held to introduce the prototype ahead of user testing. Presented during the general meeting, further refinement will remain.
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-2.4	Thematic workshops	20	02-07-2019		Two workshops have been done
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-3.2	Thematic workshops	20	30-06-2019		One workshop has been done and given input for the interview guidelines
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-3.3	Pathway analysis of exchanging signals	10		26	An interview-guideline has been developed and interviews have been performed in six countries. National as well as joint thematic analysis is ongoing.
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-3.4	Inventory and analysis of tools for horizon scanning	18	30-06-2019		In addition, an extra deliverable will be a pilot horizon scanning team exercise (see D-JIP2-3.6)
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-3.5	System analysis of detection of outbreaks	24		30	Draft of UK systems map completed Dec-2019.
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-3.7	Drivers of change in One Health– a horizon scanning exercise	30			New deliverable, not listed in the proposal. A horizon scanning exercise on was done at the general meeting in November 2019. Material compiled within 3.2 (including the exercise) will be compiled.
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-4.1	Implemented database	17	30-06-2019		The workload of this subtask was underestimated, in particular because it depended by the first workshop which was postponed to Month 11. D-JIP2-4.1 = D-4.1.1. in project description
	D-JIP2-4.2	Description of the links and the linked databases	21	30-09-2019		The report was finished and uploaded to the EJP platform end of September 2019. D-JIP2-4.2 = D-4.1.2 in project description

COHESIVE	D-JIP2-4.5	Report of available tools and algorithms and ranking of most valuable features	12	30-06-2019		The report was finished and uploaded to the EJP platform end of June 2019. D-JIP2-4.5 = D-4.2.1 in project description
COHESIVE	D-JIP2-4.8	Report section about user requirements, relevant modelling modules and final specification for a modelling tool	10	30-10-2019		The report was finished and uploaded to the EJP platform end of October 2019. D-JIP2-4.8 = D-4.3.1 in project description

Milestones

JIP name	Milestone number	Milestone name	Delivery date from AWP	Achieved (Yes / No)	If not achieved: Forecast achievement date	Comments
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-1.2	Annual report	16	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-2.1	Development of tool for systematic risk-assessment	18	Yes		
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-3.2	Pathway and system analysis of signal exchange and outbreak detection	24	No	33	Task 3.1 is currently on-going and the results will be compiled in early 2020. The preliminary draft of Task 3.3 which was done at UK level needs to be adjusted to other countries. The joint work of tasks 3.1 and 3.3 starts in 2020.
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-4.2	Prioritization of requirements for risk modeling framework	12	Yes		Typical components have been identified that support quantitative microbiological risk assessment
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-4.4	Databases for WGS data consistent with COMPARE standards, for the metadata of the samples included in the WGS database, and for the data collected by classical epidemiology investigations (case-control studies)	17	Yes		The workload of this subtask was underestimated, in particular because it depended by the first workshop which was postponed to Month 11
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-4.5	Fully operating and linked databases	21	Yes		The activity was finished and the related deliverable has been uploaded to the EJP platform end of September 2019.
COHESIVE	M-JIP2-4.6	Prototype for tracing framework ready	24	Yes		A first implementation of the tracing web portal including an interactive analysis module, a reporting module and a synchronization module with the desktop version of FoodChain-Lab (FCL) is available in a test environment. The production system of the tracing portal is currently set up and will be accessible at https://fcl-portal.bfr.berlin in early 2020. More modules will be integrated in 2020.

4. Publications and patents

No peer reviewed publications

5. Impact & relevance

A major aim of this project is to close the gap between public health, food safety and veterinary domains, mainly in the area of risk-analysis. The aim of COHESIVE is to enhance collaboration on all zoonotic threats, irrespective of the regulatory status. Earlier warning of potential zoonotic threats in a structured and integrated way, will facilitate risk management, between the human, food and veterinary domains making use of the tools to be developed in this project (implementation guideline for integrated risk-analysis, decision-tree help selecting the proper risk assessment tool, tools for foresight prediction of zoonotic threats or drivers of change). In the several workshops during specific WP meetings and general meetings, important steps were made, to develop the foreseen tools, including attracting people to participate. In addition, the workshops are good opportunities for networking over domains but also over countries. Networking also took place by the interviews performed within countries among professionals in the area of zoonoses control. An important point of attention is implementation. Developing tools is one thing, but in order to have impact implementation is crucial. Therefore, stakeholder engagement is important. For Cohesive on one hand EFSA, ECDC and EU-Commission are important stakeholders, but also national policy makers and directors of public health institutes, veterinary institutes and food safety authorities are important stakeholders as well. We would like to interest them in Cohesive by inviting them to (parts of) our activities and have the intention to organize a specific broad stakeholder meeting. By teaming up with the FAO we hope to further increase the impact of the project. The integration of One-Health information systems bringing surveillance data together within a country will further close the gap between med-vet-food and help to improve signaling in an integrated med-vet-food fashion, support tracing, support risk modelling and control. Ideally, also EFSA and ECDC would benefit from these integrated databases. The FCL tracing portal combines the effort of several projects on national and European level by integrating their outcomes in the tracing portal. The portal also integrates data from food safety and public health and thereby promotes the One Health approach. As a proof of concept, the tracing portal is used in first outbreak investigations in Member States and by EFSA. There are efforts to implement the FCL tracing portal in EFSA official tasks such as producing Rapid Outbreak Assessments in the future. Within the different meetings new contacts were made with people from other domains and expertise, bringing the related tasks to a more One Health approach.

6. Interactions with other JRPs/JIPs or with external (EU or national) relevant project

- Together with ORION and NOVA a One Health glossary is developed. ORION is in the lead with providing a web based tool. COHESIVE is providing terms which will be reviewed within Cohesive and will review terms in provided by ORION or NOVA. A manuscript is in preparation.
- There have been several contact moments with EFSA and ECDC this year. Parts of the annual/general meeting were open for all stakeholders and other EJP partners interested in Cohesive.
- There is good contact with FAO. The coordinator of Cohesive and a member of WP2 from APHA joined a meeting of the SISOT working group, led by FAO. Sean Shadomy from FAO presented the TZG and work of SISOT during the Cohesive general meeting in Rome. Also a second person from FAO was present during this meeting.
- There are links to the EJP NOVA project in which a module for analysis of sales data should be integrated into FCL. There is a close collaboration with EFSA with focus on tracing solutions in the framework of an EFSA-BfR Framework Partnership Agreement. Also, FCL was part of joint ECDC-EFSA crisis trainings. On the national level, FCL is involved in a project with the German federal state

North-Rhine Westphalia on developing a data entry mask for supply chain data. Several modules of the tracing portal were developed in the framework of these projects and the aim of COHESIVE is to unify all of them under one umbrella – the FCL tracing portal.

- Several people involved in both COHESIVE and ORION
- During the WGS workshop in Dubrovnik, connections were made with projects ORION and IRIDA team from Public Health Canada, which also deal with connecting databases.

7. *Follow-up of the recommendations and comments in previous review(s) by the Ethics Advisors*

Requirements (from ethical reviewers)	Measures and actions taken	Comments Ethics Advisors in January-February 2019	Measures and actions taken by Project Leaders at the end of 2019
none	none	none	/

8. *List of critical risks*

Description of risk	Yes/No
Loss of key-persons (staff and / or leaders)	yes
Delay in work plan execution	yes
Conflicts within the consortium	no
Lack of commitment of partners	yes
Delay in duties, tasks or reporting	yes
Poor intra-project (JRP) relationship	no
Potential entry/exit of partners	yes
Other risks (please describe)	yes

Additional information

Some of the risks identified in the beginning of the project are already solved, but some will remain and new ones arise.

Unfortunately, we had to say goodbye to Armando Giovannini. The WP leader of WP4 died suddenly. His tasks have been taken over within IZS-AM. It does not seem to lead to problems in the output.

PHE has withdrawn from the project. Due to retirement of key-personnel they could not fulfil the assigned tasks. This is not crucial to the project, but we will miss some unique expertise.

There are delays in the work plan execution, which will lead to not making all deliverables in time. However, up to this point, this does not seem to lead to problems in the final results/products.

Partners and key persons are loaded with other tasks. In addition, unforeseen crises and outbreaks in partnering countries may lead to delays in achieving the milestones. This happened in WP3, where key-personnel was engaged in control of an outbreak.

Several modules to be integrated into the tracing portal are developed in the framework of other projects. However, if such a project fails to develop a usable module, the respective module cannot be integrated into the COHESIVE tracing portal.

9. List of dissemination and communication activities

Name of the activity:	COHESIVE Annual Meeting		
Date:	10-12 April 2019		
Place:	SVA, Sweden		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	35	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	2
Policy Makers	2		

Name of the activity:	Thematic workshop in Norway – Outbreak investigation within One health across sectors		
Date:	24 th April 2019		
Place:	Norwegian Institute of Public Health, Oslo, Norway		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	yes	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	70	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Project presentation at Programme Management Committee		
Date:	9 May 2019		
Place:	ANSES, Paris		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	OHEJP Annual Scientific meeting: oral presentation: Dealing With (re)Emerging Zoonoses: A One Health Approach In The Netherlands		
Date:	20-24 May 2019		
Place:	Dublin		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	300	Media	
Industry	5	Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	5		

Name of the activity:	Meeting between German federal food safety and public health authorities: Presentation of FCL tracing portal and discussion on data needs for outbreak investigations		
Date:	29 May 2019		
Place:	Berlin		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	10	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Project presentation at "OHEJP: How is Sciensano Involved?"		
Date:	5 June 2019		
Place:	Sciensano Uccle, Brussels		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	Yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	35	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers	11		

Name of the activity:	Project presentation at Programme Owner Committee		
Date:	19 June 2019		
Place:	ANSES Paris		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	Yes
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	30	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	COHESIVE workshop on development guidelines		
Date:	1-2 July 2019		
Place:	Brussel, Sciensano		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	yes	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	15	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	WGS-based surveillance: a cog-wheel workshop to detect links and promote collaboration among OHEJP projects and external initiatives		
Date:	September 16-17 2019		
Place:	Dubrovnik Croatia		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	40	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	COHESIVE workshop on development guidelines		
Date:	8-9 October 2019		
Place:	London, APHA		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop	yes	Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	15	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	SEMINÁRIO DE COMEMORAÇÃO DO DIA MUNDIAL DA UMA SÓ SAÚDE - Quando acontece "UMA SÓ SAÚDE!" ONE HEALTH WORLD DAY CELEBRATION SEMINAR - When "ONE HEALTH!" Happens		
Date:	4 th November 2019		
Place:	Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Lisbon		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference	Yes	Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	80	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Project presentation at annual research day SVA		
Date:	12 November 2019		
Place:	Uppsala, SVA		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	yes
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	80	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	HAIRS OneHealth Workshop (Task 2.2)		
Date:	07/11/2019		
Place:	Birmingham Repertory Theatre, Birmingham		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	6	Media	
Industry	3	Investors	
Civil Society	15	Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	DES Taster Club (task 2.2/3.3)		
Date:	12/11/2019		
Place:	APHA Weybourne Building, Surrey		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	Yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)		(Internal presentation)	
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)		Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society	20	Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	SISOT working group, part of Tripartite Zoonoses Guide-group		
Date:	20-22 November		
Place:	Rome, FAO		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	Yes
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	15	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other (FAO/WHO/OIE)	10
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	COHESIVE general meeting		
Date:	27-29 November 2019		
Place:	Rome, ISS		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website		Other	yes
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	35	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	3
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	One Health Lunch (NVI and NIPH lunch together with short presentation of a relevant theme: COHESIVE project, OH EJP Summer School, OH EJP 2 nd call projects, presentation of research at NVI		
Date:	10.1, 8.3, 17.10, 8.11		
Place:	Norwegian Veterinary Institute/Norwegian Institute of Public Health		
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer		Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media		Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	yes
Website		Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)		Organisation of One Health Lunch	yes
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	5-15 per lunch event	Media	
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public		Other	
Policy Makers			

Name of the activity:	Various media activities		
Date:	Throughout 2018- 2019		
Place:			
Specify the Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the One Health EJP project for each of the following categories			
	Yes / No		Yes / No
Organisation of a Conference		Participation to a Conference	
Organisation of a Workshop		Participation to a Workshop	
Press release		Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)		Video/Film	
Exhibition		Brokerage Event	
Flyer	yes	Pitch Event	
Training		Trade Fair	
Social Media	yes	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects	
Website	yes	Other	
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)			
Specify the estimated number of persons reached, in the context of this dissemination and communication activity), in each of the following categories			
	Number		Number
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	X	Media	X
Industry		Investors	
Civil Society		Customers	
General Public	X	Other	X
Policy Makers	X		

10. List of planned tele- or video conferences, face to face meetings in the next year

- WP2.1/WP3.1 meeting, March/April 2020
- WP4 integration activity: Telco on January 2020 with BfR people, followed by a meeting at Bfr, probably on Summer 2020.
- Annual meeting, including workshops, Autumn 2020
- Stakeholder meeting 2020
- Monthly VC steering group and task leaders
- Regular VC per WP
- Regular VC with EFSA and ECDC